
N-LIST: AN EFFECTIVE E-RESOURCES FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

Information and learning Resources play a vital role in research and academic development of any institution. The involvement and vast use of ICT based tool and especially internet have made significant changes in information resources generation, storage, access and dissemination in the electronic form virtually. It influences the use and collection development method and policies of academic libraries. Libraries often prefer electronic resources as substitute to print collections for optimum utilization. INFLIBNET and INDEST-AICTE Consortiums N-LIST program is the major evolutionary initiatives in India for universities and college library users to access to e-resources to students, researchers and faculty from colleges. These revolutionary steps are providing scholarly resources including e-journals, e-books, databases, abstracts proceedings etc. virtually to users which helps to colleges for their research and development. This paper specially discusses about N-LIST Project of INFLIBNET, its components, availability of e-resources, access and retrieval, membership procedure, current status and their roles for colleges with respect to their research and development.

Keywords: INFLIBNET, N-LIST, E-Resource, E-ShodhSindhu, E-Journals, E-Books

Introduction:

Libraries play a vital role in educational institutions in supporting learning, teaching and research activities. The academic libraries working with primary goal and responsibility of to collect, manage and disseminate the information to its user according to their need. From last decades due to use of ICT technologies the traditional libraries move towards the modern libraries and also information collection in the form of traditional to Electronic (E-Books, E-Journals etc.) are the largest and fastest growing collections in the libraries. Electronic resources are the prime ingredients and in most of academic

libraries they become a common part of the library resource collection. Due to the involvement and tremendous use of ICT tools, especially the internet and the web tools, have brought significant changes in the ways of information generation, storage, dissemination, retrieval and make use of information. Recent advancement in web and digital technologies and the recent changing mode of traditional to E-publishing have brought in a revolution in publication industry; also make revolutionary changes in subscription, access and dissemination of e-publication resources (like e-journals and e-books) through digitally and virtually.

The INFLIBNET N-LIST programme of e-resources provides access to e-resources to faculty, students and researchers from subscribed colleges and other beneficiary institutions in affordable cast and the authorized users from member colleges can access, resources (e-journals, e-books) and download articles required by them directly from the publisher's website as an when required by using authenticated ID and password. They can use and store these e-resources for their academic research and development. So now days the academic libraries often prefer electronic resources to substitute print collections for optimum use.

N-LIST

The Project entitled "National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)", is an initiative of the Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India under its National Mission on Education through ICT program, which operates through its headquarter set-up at the INFLIBNET Centre, Ahmedabad, Gujarat. N-LIST was formerly launched on 4th May 2012 and being jointly executed by the e-

ShodhSindhu Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, IIT Delhi provides for i) cross-subscription to e-resources subscribed by the two Consortia, i.e. subscription to INDEST-AICTE resources for universities and e-ShodhSindhu resources for technical institutions; and ii) access to selected e-resources to colleges.

The N-LIST project provides access to e-resources to students, researchers and faculty from colleges and other beneficiary institutions through server(s) installed at the INFLIBNET Centre. The authorized users from colleges can now access e-resources and download articles required by them directly from the publisher's website (<http://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in>) with individual user id and password once they are duly authenticated as authorized users through servers deployed at the INFLIBNET Centre. The N-LIST covers all the disciplines viz. Pure Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities including Linguistic and Languages. However e-resources in engineering, agriculture and medicine are not covered under the N-LIST programme.

Fig. NLIST e-resources Portal (Source: <https://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in/>)

NLIST Portal URL: <https://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in>

NLIST Present User Status as on 30/9/2022:

- ◆ Beneficiary Colleges: 4019
- ◆ Total Active Users: 631824
- ◆ Users Activated in Sep-2022: 116977

N-LIST Components

The four distinct components of N-LIST Project are

- i) To subscribe and provide access to selected e-ShodhSindhu e-resources to technical institutions (IITs, IISc, IISERs and NITs) and monitor its usage
- ii) To subscribe and provide access to selected INDEST e-resources to selected universities and monitor its usage
- iii) To subscribe and provide access of selected e-resources to Govt./ Govt.-aided colleges and monitor its usage
- iv) To act as a Monitoring Agency for colleges and evaluate, promote, impart training and monitor all activities involved in the process of providing effective and efficient access to e-resources to colleges

The INDEST and UGC-INFONET are jointly responsible for activity listed at i) and ii) above. The INFLIBNET Centre, Gandhinagar is responsible for activities listed at iii) and iv) above. The INFLIBNET Centre is also responsible for developing and deploying appropriate software tools and techniques for authenticating authorized users.

N-LIST Membership Procedure:

Faculty, staff, students and researchers from colleges covered under the 12B/2F

NLIST Membership Fees Structure:

As per INFLIBNET guideline the N-LIST project provides access to e-resources to students, researchers and faculty from

Act of UGC are eligible to access e-resources through the N-LIST project.

Steps to get Membership from NLIST for Colleges

- ◆ Fill the registration form online. (Details about College, Administrator & Fees etc.) in <http://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in/> website.
- ◆ Enclose 12B certificate issued by UGC. Eligible colleges will be received a confirmation e-mail regarding registration within 3-4 days after registration.
- ◆ Colleges will have to generate Proforma Invoice from the NLIST Website. The membership fees have to be made by DD or through RTGS / NEFT as mentioned details in Proforma Invoice.
- ◆ Obtain College Administrator's username and password to create user name and password for faculty members and students from INFLIBNET Centre by sending an authorisation letter of contact person.
- ◆ College Administrator can create user name and password for faculty members and students instantly or upload bulk users after log-in College Administrator Module.
- ◆ Login at the N-LIST website i.e. <http://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in>
- ◆ **To User Access-** Users will have to click on Member's Login through NLIST Website <http://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in/> and login. It will display list of e-resources subscribed under the programme. Click at the desired e-resource to access its full-text.
- ◆ The period of membership is valid from April to March every financial year.

colleges covered under the 12B/2F Act of UGC are eligible to access e-resources through the N-LIST project

- ♦ All colleges covered under Section 12B of UGC Act will be required to pay an annual membership fee of Rs 5,900.00/- (Rs. 5000/- Membership Fee + Rs. 900/- (18%) GST)
- ♦ Non aided colleges (except Agriculture, Engineering, Medical, Pharmacy and Nursing) will be required to pay an annual membership fee of Rs. 35,400.00/- (Rs. 30,000/-Membership Fee + Rs.5400/- (18%) GST)

Infrastructure/ICT Requirement for Accessing N-LIST Electronic Resources:

To access NLIST resources a minimum level of ICT requirement of hardware and software is a pre-requisite for a user or subscribing institution desirous of subscribing e-resources so as to achieve efficient and effective interaction with subscribed NLIST e-resources. Though all e-resources subscribed and provided by the INFLIBNET NLIST program are available through web-based/Internet, hence for accessing e-resources through N-LIST Colleges should have adequate number of Internet-enabled PCs and Internet connectivity for accessing e-resources 24*7. Specialty high speed broadband internet connectivity recommended to get better and uninterrupted access to e-resources.

Current Status of Membership:

As on 20th February 2021 a total number of 3,706 beneficiary colleges have registered themselves with the N-LIST including Govt.-aided colleges covered under Sections 12(B) and 2(f) of UGC Act as well as non-aided colleges. All e-resources subscribed for colleges under the N-LIST are now accessible to these colleges through N-LIST website (<http://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in>). Total no. of current active users is 5, 54,979 and 47020 users activated in month of February-2022.

NLIST service Beneficiaries:

All college covered under Sections 12(B) and 2(f) of the UGC Act and Non-aided Colleges (except for colleges imparting education in Agriculture, Engineering, Management, Medical, Pharmacy, Dentistry and Nursing) are eligible to access selected e-resources subscribed for the colleges under e-Shodh Sindhu. These resources include 6,150 e-journals and 31,64,309 e-books. All eligible colleges are required to register themselves online.

Electronic Resources Available under the N-LIST Programme:

Under the membership of NLIST program beneficiary member colleges, registered for the N-LIST, a college component of E-Shodh Sindhu, can access 6,150 electronic journals and 1,64,309 electronic books including e-books available through national subscription.

Table 1: Full-text Electronic Resources (E-Journals)

Sl. No.	E-resources	Publishing Country	No. of Journals	Back-file from	Resource URL
1	American Institute of Physics	USA	18	Ten yrs	http://journals.aip.org/
2	Annual Reviews	USA	33	Ten yrs	http://arjournals.annualreviews.org/
3	Economic and	India	1	1966+	http://www.epw.in/

	Political Weekly (EPW)				
4	Indian Journals	India	186	2007+	http://www.indianjournals.com/
5	Institute of Physics	UK	46	Vol. 1+	http://iopscience.iop.org/
6	JSTOR	USA	2500	Vol. 1+	http://www.jstor.org/
7	Oxford University Press	UK	262	1996+	https://academic.oup.com/journals
8	Royal Society of Chemistry	UK	29	Ten yrs	http://pubs.rsc.org/en/journals?key=title&value=current
9	H. W. Wilson	USA	3,075	1982+	http://search.ebscohost.com
10	Cambridge University Press (2010-2016)	UK	224	Ten yrs	https://www.cambridge.org/core

Table 2: Electronic Books (E-Books)

Sl. No.	E-book Name	Publishing Country	Books	Resource URL
1	E-brary	USA	1,850,00+	https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/inflibnet-ebooks
2	Cambridge Books Online	UK	1,800	https://www.cambridge.org/core
3	EBSCO Host-Net Library	USA	936	http://search.ebscohost.com
4	Hindustan Book Agency	India	65	https://portal.igpublish.com/iglibrary/
5	Institute of South East Asian Studies (ISEAS) Books	India	382	https://portal.igpublish.com/iglibrary/
6	Oxford Scholarship Online	UK	1,402	http://www.oxfordscholarship.com/
7	Springer eBooks	Germany	2,300	http://link.springer.com
8	Taylor & Francis eBooks	UK	1,800	https://www.taylorfrancis.com/
9	Mylibrary-McGraw Hill	USA	1,124	https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/inflibnet-ebooks
10	Sage Publication eBooks	UK	1,000	http://knowledge.sagepub.com

E-Resources Available through National Subscription

The E-resources i.e. Access to South Asia Archives (SAA) and World E-Book Library (WEL), subscribed by eShodh Sindhu on behalf of National Digital Library (NDL), are made available to member colleges of NLIST Programme through proxy server set up at INFLIBNET Centre.

Sl. No.	Name of Collection	No. of Titles	URL Address
1	South Asia Archive [through NDL]	30,00,000+	http://www.southasiaarchive.com
2	World e-Books Library [Now available through NDLI only]	4.5 million pages	https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/

INFLIBNET N-LIST Request Service: Request an Article Service for N-LIST Members

INFLIBNET provides request an article service only to its active member colleges/institution from their website. The INFLIBNET Centre provides Inter Library Loan (ILL) service to member colleges for the benefit of NLIST users from colleges/institutions enrolled under the N-LIST program. In this service from member colleges all faculty, staff and students of member colleges are welcomed to use this service from NLIST website and request required articles of journal and chapters from books that are not available through resources subscribed under the N-LIST. The requests for articles of user can be sent online using Online Inter Library Loan methods. For user journal/Book article request form available on the N-LIST website. This service provided by the INFLIBNET is free of charge to NLIST user. For this service users are required to log-in with their NLIST user ID and password to request for articles using N-LIST ILL Service. The user's credentials for ILL request are the same that have been provided to the users in colleges for accessing N-LIST resources.

Benefits/Advantages of NLIST:

The main advantages of INFLIBNET NLIST programme are

- ♦ Remote access to e-resources (e-journals, e-books etc.) with User Id and password
- ♦ Availability and remote access of e-resources to colleges at affordable cost
- ♦ Provides multiple access of 24 *7 a week virtually
- ♦ Updated issues of journals with archives availability

- ♦ Access and retrieval of articles of reputed, Popular and quality publication from globe
- ♦ Helps to Increase research and development of students, researchers and faculties of colleges

Conclusion:

The project N-LIST becomes a major emerging and widely used consortia platform in India which acts as boon for traditional academic colleges by providing scholarly e-resources like e-journals, e-books etc. in minimal charges with high value knowledge at doorstep. It helps to colleges for their research and development and it is also very helpful to faculties, researchers and students to improve their learning and research development activity. Hence, N-LIST E-Resources are considered a vital part of academic college in Indian higher education system due to its virtual methods and way of seeking information towards electronic resources.

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